

MODERN ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS.

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Annotation: Today, the demand for information about environmental changes that are causing a lot of discussion in our society, which are happening around us, as well as the whole world, is increasing every day. This article will show with scientific reviews and specific figures the impact of the human factor on modern environmental problem sand the solution of problems, a brief analysis of the environmental problems observed in the world stage and Uzbekistan at present.

Keywords: Nitric oxide, chlorformethanes, pesticides, agro-industrial, ozonosphere, ultraviolet rays, dimming.

An ecological problem is a reaction of nature to a person in connection with the impact of man on nature, i.e. processes of economic importance in society, related to natural phenomena (climate change, mass migration or extermination of animals, damage to the world of self, etc.) is understood as any event. Natural, natural anthropogenic phenomena observed around the world are considered universal problems. We will give some examples of such problems.

"The phenomenon of atmospheric warming". The atmosphere in later years it becomes known that the content of SO_2 is increasing. In 100 years, $0.5-1.0 S^0$ has increased. Climate change on a large scale is associated with atmospheric industrial emissions and gases emitted by motor vehicles. Global warming of the earth's surface (atmospheric warming) is due to the increase of SO_2 in the air, the cutting of forests, the accumulation of SO_2 gas in the atmosphere from fuels such as coal and gasoline. It can increase by $1.5-4.5S^0$.

As a result:

1. Climate change, especially the increase in desertification.
2. Changes in precipitation.
3. Shifting of geographical zones.
4. Sea and ocean level rise.
5. Melting and reduction of glaciers and other events are observed.

Depletion of the ozone layer. Ozonosphere is an important component of the atmosphere, it affects the climate and all living organisms on the earth's surface. The most important feature of ozone in the atmosphere is its constant formation and decay. Ozone is formed by the interaction of oxygen, nitrogen oxides and other gases under the influence of sunlight. Ozone protects living organisms below the surface of the earth by absorbing strong ultraviolet rays. Exposure to ultraviolet rays causes skin burns in humans. Today, it was found that skin cancer is caused by these rays. Due to the widespread use of chlorofluoromethanes (freons) and nitrogen fertilizers, aviation gases, detonation of atomic bombs.

allows a large amount of azan to accumulate in the atmosphere. Therefore, it is planned to reduce the use of freon used in refrigerators in household life and gradually stop production.

Fresh water problem. Fresh water on land and its biosphere is very important. The amount of fresh water in the hydrosphere is very small (2-2.5%). Fresh water reserves are mainly polar ice caps. With the development of society, the population's demand for fresh water is increasing. In our century, the use of fresh water has increased 7 times. 3-3.5 thousand km² of water is consumed per year. At the end of our century, this indicator will probably increase 1.5-2 times.

The problem of pesticide use. These toxic chemicals group of weeds, harmful insects and other animals, in themselves used in the fight against disease-causing microorganisms. Spraying of pesticides in agriculture and forestry with the help of aviation leads to environmental pollution on a large scale. Pesticides spread in the atmosphere over long distances and accumulate in fields, rivers, lakes and oceans through water. The most dangerous part is that they join the ecological food chain and pass from the soil to plants, then to animals and birds, and finally to human organisms. Pesticides cause harmful conditions at every stage. Pesticides are harmful to nature and humans, and they are also stable substances against external environmental factors.

Environmental problems in Uzbekistan. Today, Uzbekistan is a large industrial and agrarian region, and in the future, it is planned to further develop the machine-building, energy, chemical, food industry, and transport complex facing the world. However, the development of productive forces has a certain negative impact on the state of social ecotourism in the republic. The modern ecological and nature protection problems that are urgent in the republic are as follows:

1. Problems of environmental protection in areas where large regional industrial complexes are located.
2. The problems of the island and the coast of the island, protection of water resources and their optimal use.
3. Environmental problems in the agro-industrial complex.
4. Natural waters with industrial waste, pesticides and mineral fertilizers
5. Problems of protection and restoration of flora and fauna, expansion of the network of nature reserves and national parks.

Prevention of modern environmental problems. It is known that in the development of any country and the improvement of the lifestyle of the population, it is important to observe three principles:

1. Economic growth
2. Social protection
3. Environmental safety

We will now focus on the third principle. A special place is given to the issue of ecological security of Uzbekistan. In general, the ecological situation in Uzbekistan, ecological security, elimination of the consequences of the environmental tragedy of the Island and the entire island, which imitates this security and has now become a global problem, and the issues of rational use of transboundary river water have not been paid attention to yesterday or today. Ecological situations have always been in the center of attention.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the origin of any modern problem, the influence of the human factor is felt. Before these problems become more widespread, we urge everyone to reduce their impact and take care of nature. After all, the way we treat nature, we can get a hundredfold from it!

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